

What Are The Various Ways To Treat CVI (Chronic Venous Insufficiency)?

Veins are a kind of circuit that returns blood towards the direction of the heart. It is the single way through which deoxygenated blood is brought back to the heart from there it goes to the lungs for the purification process. Veins consist of one-way directional valves that promote blood flow to the heart and prevent mixing the deoxygenated blood with oxygenated. Over time the walls start to weaken leading to damage. Visit **vein center** when you decide that there is a need of getting [vein treatment](#).

What are the causes?

Vein valve damage may cause venous insufficiency. When valve failure occurs a larger column of blood falls onto the next intact valve that may obstruct the blood flow in the backward direction. The abnormal blood flow may cause stretches in the surrounding vein segment leading to venous insufficiency. You may experience superficial veins, bulging out from the surface of the skin leading to varicose veins. Such types of conditions require **vein treatment la Jolla**.

How To Diagnose?

The diagnosis of varicose veins starts with a medical examination and documentation of the visible symptoms and the affected areas of dilated veins at the **vein center California**. Since the majority of varicose veins are the result of underlying venous insufficiency, the

ultrasound is the important step regarding the diagnosis of the condition. This step is necessary as it helps determine the accurate mode of **vein treatment in California**.

Varicose **vein treatment san Jose** is mainly based on improving or eliminating symptoms from the affected area.

Compression Stockings:

Compression stockings provide external compression to the legs. The technique behind this is to force blood out of the dilated veins. This compression will help in reducing the fluid pressure within the leg making it easier to relieve the varicose veins symptoms. You can purchase them from a **vein doctor** at [vein center san Diego](#).

Ambulatory phlebectomy:

It is an outpatient method designed by dermatologic surgeons that extract superficial veins through the small incisions in the skin. The veins size more than four mm in diameter needs cluster removal using tiny 2-3 mm incisions. These treatment options are recognized by the size and the severity of the affected veins.

Sclerotherapy:

This method uses a saline solution known as sclerosant that is injected directly into the diseased vein or lymph vessel. The solution makes the diseased veins collapse and disappear eventually.

Endovenous laser Treatment:

It is an advanced technology that involves laser techniques to heat the varicose veins in order to reduce them. A laser is a device that transmits a thin beam of radiation in the form of light. It closes and shrinks the varicose veins causing scar tissue within the vessel. This makes the process of blood flow through the healthy veins.

Radiofrequency Ablation:

This method uses heat produced by radio waves to treat varicose veins. It is a minimally invasive treatment, used to heat damage the wall inside a vein.

Get the following treatments done only by a **vein doctor California** at a certified **vein center san Jose** to get efficient results.

Cost of varicose vein treatments:

Name of the treatment	cost
Compression Stockings	\$10 - \$100 per pair, depending on what kind you want to buy.
Ambulatory phlebectomy	\$1,000 to \$3,000 per leg depending on the severity and the number of veins removed
Sclerotherapy	\$400-600, depending on the aforementioned factors
Endovenous laser Treatment	\$600 to \$3,000, depending on the numbers on the vein needs to be treated
Radiofrequency Ablation:	RFA procedure may cost about \$5,411